

OVERVIEW

The 2nd Bengkulu International Financial and Capital Market **Summit 2024**

DECEMBER 2024

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Welcome Remarks

Artha Sary Br Limbong

Chairperson of Capital Market Study Group,
Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Bengkulu

The honourable Ladies and Gentlemen.

Good morning and welcome to **The 2nd Bengkulu International Financial and Capital Market Summit 2024**. I am Artha Sary Br Limbong, Chairperson of the Capital Market Study Group at Bengkulu University, and it is my honor to **welcome everyone** here today.

As we reflect on the journey of **GI on the Move**, our initiative has been an exciting and fulfilling effort to engage a broad and diverse audience—from high school students to university scholars, rural communities, and others. Since our launch in July, we have organized various programs aimed at fostering financial literacy and promoting capital market awareness. Events such as the **FOMO Webinar**, the **SAFE Webinar**, the **Rafflesia Trading Extravaganza**, and the **Youth Debate and Stocklab Competitions** have enabled us to reach over 600 participants from all across Indonesia. These efforts were driven by our belief in creating a more inclusive financial ecosystem, bridging gaps in knowledge, and empowering people to make informed, responsible investment decisions.

Today, as we gather here for **The 2nd FinCap Summit**, we are thrilled to welcome industry leaders and experts who will share their invaluable insights into the future of finance. Our discussions will provide us with essential perspectives on the opportunities and challenges facing capital markets, as well as the evolving global financial landscape.

We are deeply grateful to all the parties who have supported us, including our university, institutions, organizations, and companies. Your kind contributions have been instrumental in the success of this initiative, and we truly appreciate your trust and collaboration.

I would also like to take a moment to acknowledge the dedication and hard work of our committee members. Their tireless efforts in organizing this event have been instrumental in bringing us all together. We hope that this summit serves as a meaningful contribution to the development of financial knowledge and market practices in Indonesia and over the world .

Finally, I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to all of you for being here today. Your presence and participation are greatly appreciated, and I look forward to the conversations and insights that will arise as we explore the future of finance and capital markets together. With that, I would like to respectfully hand over the session to our Master of Ceremony.

Thank you for your time and attention, and I hope you find the summit both insightful and inspiring.

Welcoming Speech

Mukti Trio Putra, S.M., MBA.

Deputy Advisor of Investment Gallery,
Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Bengkulu

Assalamualaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh.

Good morning, esteemed guests, speakers, and participants.

It is both an honor and a pleasure to welcome you all to **the 2nd Bengkulu International Financial and Capital Market Summit 2024.**

- The Honorable The Vice Dean for Student Affairs, Alumni, and Partnerships of the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Bengkulu, Dr. Rina Suthia Hayu;
- The Honorable Behavioral Analyst in Financial Services Supervision, Consumer Protection, and Strategic Management Services, Mrs. Flora Apriani;
- The Honorable Head of Indonesia Stock Exchange Bengkulu, Mrs. Marina Rasyada;
- The Respected Speakers of The 2nd Bengkulu International Finance and Capital Market Summit 2024;
- Our heartfelt appreciation also goes to faculty members, student organizations within the University of Bengkulu, the Capital Market Study Groups from across Indonesia, and all our honored guests and participants of **the 2nd Bengkulu International Finance and Capital Market Summit 2024.**

Today, we gather under the theme, "**The Influence of Global Issues: Strategic Planning for Long-Term Investment**", a topic that resonates strongly in today's rapidly changing global environment.

On behalf of Mr. Ferry Tema Atmaja, the Chief Advisor of our Investment Gallery, FEB Universitas Bengkulu, I would like to extend a warm welcome to each of you. Although Mr. Ferry could not be with us in person today, I am privileged to represent him and convey his support for this significant gathering. We are especially grateful for the presence of our esteemed speakers, whose insights and expertise elevate the quality of this event and provide invaluable perspectives on navigating the complexities of the global economy. I believe that summits like this serve as critical platforms for cultivating insightful discussions, exploring challenges and opportunities, and ultimately guiding future investment decisions in light of global economic dynamics.

In closing, I wish to express our sincere gratitude to our speakers, distinguished guests, and the organizing committee for their efforts in making this summit possible. May today's discussions inspire strategic approaches and meaningful progress toward sustainable investments that will benefit both our communities and the broader economy.

Thank you, and welcome once again to **the 2nd Bengkulu International Financial and Capital Market Summit**, and enjoy this event.

Keynote Speech

Flora Apriani

Behavioral Analyst in Financial Services Supervision,
Consumer Protection, and Strategic Management
Services, Financial Services Authority (OJK) Bengkulu

Bismillahirrahmanirrahim,

- The Honorable Ms. Rina Suthia Hayu as the Vice Dean for Student Affairs, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Bengkulu, along with her team;
- The Honorable Mrs. Marina Rasyada, Head Office of Indonesia Stock Exchange Bengkulu;
- The Honorable Mr. Mukti Trio Putra as Deputy Advisor to the Investment Gallery of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Bengkulu;
- Distinguished speakers and esteemed guests;
- And all members of the **Capital Market Study Group (KSPM) FEB UNIB**, and **participants of the 2nd International Summit**.

First of all, let us express our gratitude to the presence of God Almighty for the abundance of His grace, so that we can gather here today to discuss a very important topic: **"The Influence of Global Issues; Strategic Planning for Long-Term Investment"**.

On behalf of the Head Bengkulu Financial Services Authority (OJK) Office, **I am honored to be able to share insights that underline the important role of strategic planning in facing today's global environmental challenges**. I am genuinely honored to be here, surrounded by such exceptional speakers—each an esteemed expert and leader in their field. Their insights and experiences are truly invaluable, and I am eager to learn from them today. It is a rare privilege to hear directly from professionals who possess a profound understanding of the global market's complexities and who can guide us through these challenges with remarkable clarity and expertise.

Additionally, I want to express **Kelompok Studi Pasar Modal (KSPM) FEB UNIB** for starting and planning this project such initiatives demonstrate a remarkable dedication to teaching students and the community about the capital market and offering a forum for discussion. In addition to increasing financial literacy, this initiative trains the next generation for investors to be prudent and responsible.

It is hoped that the KSPM will stay active and grow in the future by producing constructive initiative like this. The topic of our discussion **"The Impact of Global Issues: Strategic Planning for Long-Term Investment"** is highly pertinent and significant. Particularly in the like of the current state of the world economy. We must develop a thorough understanding and sophisticated strategic planning to make sure that the investment we make can actually yield long-term gains in the face of market volatility, geopolitical concerns. Monetary Public changes and other difficulties.

Keynote Speech (contd.)

The financial service authority (OJK) which is in charge of regulating the financial service industry in Indonesia, plays a crucial role in maintaining the stability, health and transparency of the country's capital market. OJK educates the public in addition to focusing on regulation. The goal of this education is to guarantee that all participants in the market including students and aspiring young investors have a sufficient awareness of the potential and hazard in the capital market through a number of regulations and stringent oversight procedures. **OJK contributes to safeguarding investors' interests in terms of supervising.** We make certain that participants in the capital markets including securities firms, public listed companies and others, follow the rules of ethical business practice and sound government governance. This is crucial in order to provide the public confidence in the capital market investing. Particularly in light of the global economic uncertainty that frequently impacts market performance. In order to give the public the knowledge they need to make informed investment decisions, OJK also occasionally offers financial literacy and information, including campaigns on safe and smart investing.

We think that investors, especially students, as the next generations, can establish sustainable investing strategies by using the relevant information and making informed choices. At the moment, it is impossible to isolate the impact of numerous international crises from Indonesia's capital market. In the model of globalization, the Indonesian economy, especially its capital market, is frequently directly impacted by economic changes in major nations like United States of America, China, or the United Kingdom. Global concerns that frequently impact our capital market include changes in commodity prices, geopolitical unpredictability, and monetary policies in wealthy nations.

For instance, foreign capital flows frequently move from developing nations like Indonesia to developed nations when the US raises its benchmark interest rate. This is why we see a drop in stock prices in our capital market, geopolitical disputes or trade wars can also cause uncertainty that makes investors more worried and disrupt the global supply chain. Other instances that impact our market are the energy crisis and changes in global energy sector policies. Companies in Indonesia may be directly impacted by changes in energy costs brought on by geopolitical unrest and energy transition policies.

Particularly those that rely on the export of commodities energy. In light of all of this, **it is critical that we as market participants constantly update data and examine world trends.** Investors can manage their investment more methodically and strategically if they are aware of how this problem affects our financial markets. For young investors such as the student present here, I would like to emphasize **the importance of understanding the value of long-term investing.** The capital market has shortened fluctuations that are often difficult to predict. However, with careful planning and good risk management, we can still achieve optimal results.

Keynote Speech (contd.)

There are three principles that I would like to convey for long-term investment strategies.

- First, **portfolio diversification**. Don't put all your assets in one type of investment. By diversifying, you reduce risk and make your portfolio more resilient to fluctuating.
- Second, **avoiding high-risk investment without a basis**. Avoid following trends without a strong understanding every dedication must be based on in-depth analysis.
- And last, **investing according to a financial plan**. Plan your investment based on your financial goals. Whatever your goals are for the long-term, such as retirement or for the short term, determine a strategy according to your needs.

Students and general public in attendance should keep in mind that investing in a component of a long-term life plan and is not solely about changing quick reaches. We may attend financial stability in the future and take part in the growth of international capital market. In my opinion, if we apply investing techniques with discipline and a solid understanding.

Once again, thank you for the opportunity given to me and my deepest appreciation goes to KSPM for their hard work. I hope this event can provide new insight and raise the to continue learning and investing wisely.

Before closing my work, allow me to convey a "pantun." Please help me to say nice or thumbs up.

Bengkulu's brings , Indonesia's pride
Learning together side by side
Long-term goals, steady and strong
for a brighter future, we all belong.

Second,
In Bengkulu breeze, the future calls
With knowledge share, we take our stand
Indonesia's growth, it never stops
Investing wisely across this land.

Wassalamualaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh.

Opening Speech

Dr. Rina Suthia Hayu, SE., MM.

Vice Dean for Student Affairs, Alumni, and Partnerships
Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Bengkulu

Good Morning,

- The Honorable Mrs. Flora Apriani, Analyst in the Financial Services Business Conduct Supervision, Education, Consumer Protection, and Strategic Management Services Division, at the Financial Service Authority Bengkulu, along with her team;
- The Honorable Mrs. Marina Rasyada, Head Office of Indonesia Stock Exchange Bengkulu;
- The Honorable Mr. Mukti Trio Putra, Deputy Advisor to the Investment Gallery of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Bengkulu;
- Distinguished speakers and esteemed guests, and distinguished members of the Kelompok Studi Pasar Modal and GIBEI FEB UNIB, and all participants of **The 2nd International Summit 2024**.

First and foremost, let us offer our gratitude to Almighty God for His blessings and grace, enabling us to gather here today for the 2nd International Summit 2024 under the theme **“The Influence of Global Issues; Strategic Planning for Long-Term Investing”**.

I would also like to convey an apologies on behalf of the Rector of University of Bengkulu, who was originally scheduled to open this event but is unable to join us today. Therefore, I have been entrusted with the honor of representing him in officially opening this summit.

As Vice Dean, I am truly proud to be part of this occasion. The 2nd International Summit marks the peak event of GI on the Move 2024, organized by the Capital Market Study Group (KSPM) FEB UNIB. This organization has consistently demonstrated exceptional dedication in advancing financial and capital market literacy across various groups.

In the face of increasingly complex and challenging global developments, such as climate change, geopolitical uncertainty, and rapid technological transformation, the need for sound long-term investment planning has become more pressing. **This summit**, therefore, **serves as an invaluable forum** to expand our perspectives on developing responsive and sustainable investment strategies, capable of making positive contributions to the economy at both local and global levels.

I would also like to extend my sincerest admiration and praise to our remarkable and highly dedicated speakers, who have generously shared their time and expertise with us today. Their commitment to deepening our understanding of these crucial issues and their wealth of knowledge will undoubtedly enrich our discussions. Their presence is a testament to the value of collaboration and the pursuit of knowledge, which are essential as we navigate an ever-evolving global landscape.

Opening Speech (contd.)

I extend my sincere appreciation to the Capital Market Study Group for their hard work in organizing this event and for bringing together such highly competent professionals in the field. My hope is that the discussions and presentations during this summit will serve as a source of inspiration and knowledge to guide us in navigating global uncertainties with wiser and more visionary investment approaches.

With that, **I hereby declare The 2nd International Financial and Capital Market Summit 2024 officially open.**

Wassalamualaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh.

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Webinar

Balancing Profit and Responsibility in Investing Decisions

Overview

- Speaker* The webinar offered a comprehensive exploration of sustainable investment practices and their integration into Indonesia's capital market. Key topics included the introduction of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles, their role in promoting sustainable economic growth, and the mechanisms of carbon trading through the IDX Carbon Exchange.
- Edwin Hartanto**
IDX Carbon
- Moderator*
- Mukti Trio Putra**
Universitas Bengkulu

The session focused on balancing financial returns with ethical and environmental considerations, highlighting the role of ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) investments in tackling global challenges like climate change through innovative financial strategies. The interactive Q&A allowed participants to explore key issues, such as how to align profitability with sustainability, promote sustainable practices in MSMEs, and ensure the integrity of carbon trading mechanisms. The presenter's comprehensive responses provided practical insights, emphasizing how ESG principles can guide responsible investing and enhance long-term risk management.

Introduction

Climate change, a defining megatrend of the 21st century, is reshaping global financial markets and driving the integration of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors into investment strategies. The webinar explored the critical intersection between financial performance and ethical responsibility, particularly in the context of sustainability and climate action. It addressed pressing questions about how investors can balance profitability with responsible practices while navigating the challenges posed by this transformative trend.

The global shift toward sustainability has made it imperative for investors to integrate ESG principles into their decision-making processes. This transition is driven by the recognition that environmental and social factors, such as carbon emissions, climate risks, and economic inequality, are no longer externalities but critical considerations for long-term investment stability. Furthermore, Indonesia's unique position as a growing market with significant contributions to global sustainability efforts, particularly through initiatives like the IDX Carbon Exchange, makes this discussion both timely and vital.

The primary goal of the webinar was to deepen participants' understanding of the growing importance of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles in investment decision-making. It aimed to introduce the concept of carbon trading and its integration into Indonesia's financial ecosystem through the IDX Carbon Exchange, highlighting its alignment with global climate commitments under the Paris Agreement.

Beyond imparting knowledge, the webinar aimed to inspire meaningful action, urging participants—ranging from students and academics to practitioners and investors—to consider the long-term implications of their decisions on both the economy and the environment. By emphasizing the importance of innovation and sustainability, the session highlighted pathways for Indonesia's capital market to harmonize profitability with responsibility. Furthermore, the webinar sought to equip participants with practical strategies to integrate sustainability into project management, enabling them to achieve financial objectives while advancing environmental goals and fostering a more sustainable economic future.

Format & Methodology

The webinar was conducted on Friday, November 15, 2024, from 9:45 AM to 11:00 AM (GMT +7) via Zoom Meeting, featuring an engaging and interactive talk show format. Over 75 minutes, the session includes an opening and introduction (5 minutes), presentation time (45 minutes), a Q&A session (15 minutes), and a closing statement and summary (10 minutes), fostering active participation between speakers and the audience. Designed for university students in finance and economics, as well as practitioners and academics interested in sustainable investing.

Discussions

ESG Principles and Their Relevance

The webinar began by introducing Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles and their increasing importance in the financial landscape. Mr. Edwin Hartanto explained how ESG provides a framework for integrating sustainability into investment decisions, marking a shift from purely profit-driven strategies to a balanced approach that addresses long-term risks and ethical responsibilities. He highlighted challenges such as climate change, inequality, and governance issues while promoting the triple bottom line concept—profit, people, and planet. Through examples like the Enron scandal, Mr. Hartanto demonstrated how neglecting governance and sustainability can lead to significant consequences, underscoring the necessity of ethical governance and transparency.

Mr. Edwin Hartanto also discussed the progress made in adopting ESG principles in Indonesia's capital market, supported by regulatory initiatives and corporate compliance. An increasing number of companies are now submitting sustainability reports alongside financial disclosures, providing investors with a comprehensive view of their operations. He highlighted the introduction of ESG-focused indexes, such as IDX ESG Leaders and IDX LQ45 Low Carbon Leaders, which have facilitated sustainable investment. These indexes, which consistently outperform conventional ones, exemplify the economic and environmental potential of ESG-aligned practices.

Carbon Trading and the IDX Carbon Exchange

A central topic of the webinar was the role of carbon trading in addressing climate change, particularly through the IDX Carbon Exchange. Mr. Hartanto explained that

carbon trading is an essential mechanism for reducing greenhouse gas emissions, in line with the goals of the Paris Agreement. He outlined how carbon pricing mechanisms, such as emission trading systems (ETS), work to create financial incentives for businesses to reduce their carbon emissions. The IDX Carbon Exchange serves as a platform where companies can buy and sell carbon credits generated from environmental projects like renewable energy initiatives and reforestation. This trading system supports Indonesia's national emission reduction targets, while providing a cost-effective method for companies to meet sustainability obligations. Mr. Hartanto also pointed out the importance of validating carbon credits through rigorous monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) processes to ensure their credibility and prevent greenwashing.

Sustainability Reporting and Regulatory Support

Mr. Hartanto highlighted the increasing importance of sustainability reporting as part of the regulatory framework governing Indonesia's capital market. He explained that sustainability reports are now as important as financial statements for listed companies, as these reports provide crucial information about a company's environmental and social impacts. He also discussed the role of regulators, such as Indonesia's Financial Services Authority (OJK), in mandating the publication of these reports. Additionally, Mr. Hartanto emphasized the introduction of a "green taxonomy" by OJK, which categorizes business sectors based on their sustainability practices. This taxonomy helps investors and financial institutions identify and support businesses that align with sustainability goals, thus ensuring that capital flows towards environmentally responsible projects.

The Growth of ESG-Focused Financial Products

Mr. Hartanto discussed the rise of ESG-focused financial products in Indonesia's capital market, including green bonds, sustainability-linked bonds, and other investment vehicles. These products have allowed investors to directly support projects that align with sustainability goals, such as renewable energy or climate change mitigation projects. Mr. Hartanto provided examples of how asset owners, including insurance companies and pension funds, are increasingly including ESG criteria in their investment portfolios. By investing in such products, these asset owners

can both support the global sustainability agenda and meet growing demand for responsible investment options. He also discussed the emergence of green financing, which is an innovative approach that links financing with specific environmental or social outcomes, demonstrating how ESG practices are now integrated into the broader financial ecosystem.

Indonesia’s Role in Global Sustainable Investment Trends

Mr. Hartanto also explored Indonesia’s role within the global sustainable finance landscape. He noted that foreign investment in ESG-aligned projects is growing rapidly, particularly in the European and Asian markets. As international investors demand more sustainable investment options, Indonesia has the opportunity to attract foreign capital by improving its sustainability practices. The speaker emphasized that the country’s commitment to reducing carbon emissions and adopting renewable energy sources will be crucial in securing this influx of investment. He highlighted that Indonesia’s rich natural resources and its focus on sustainability could make it a key player in global sustainable finance, particularly through initiatives like carbon trading and green bonds.

Key Questions and Responses

Question 1: How can investors balance financial returns with ethical responsibility in sustainable investments? This question explores the intersection of profitability and ethical responsibility in sustainable investing.

Response: Mr. Hartanto explained that achieving this balance involves integrating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles into investment strategies. By prioritizing both short-term financial returns and long-term risk mitigation—such as environmental and social risks—investors can align their portfolios with sustainability goals. Tools like ESG criteria and green bonds were highlighted as practical mechanisms for achieving this dual objective. Furthermore, he emphasized the growing role of responsible investing in promoting societal and environmental progress alongside financial performance.

Question 2: What are carbon offsets, and how do they contribute to achieving net zero? This question seeks to clarify the concept of carbon offsets and their role in emission reduction strategies.

Response: Mr. Hartanto defined carbon offsets as market instruments allowing companies to compensate for unavoidable emissions by supporting verified projects aimed at reducing or removing greenhouse gases. Examples include investments in renewable energy or reforestation projects. He highlighted their significance in achieving net-zero goals, emphasizing that offsets enable firms to address residual emissions effectively. However, he cautioned against potential risks such as "greenwashing" and stressed the importance of ensuring offsets' credibility through third-party verification and adherence to stringent quality standards.

Question 3: How can data credibility in carbon trading be ensured? This question addresses a critical challenge in maintaining transparency and trust in carbon markets.

Response: Mr. Hartanto detailed the role of the **Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV)** process, underpinned by independent **Validation and Verification Bodies (VVBs)**. These third-party entities audit carbon projects to ensure compliance with rigorous international standards before credits are issued. By implementing such robust oversight, the IDX Carbon Exchange aims to foster transparency, enhance data integrity, and mitigate risks of misinformation or fraudulent activities in the carbon trading ecosystem.

Question 4: What is the role of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in sustainable investing, and how can they overcome sustainability barriers? This question examines the contribution of MSMEs to sustainable practices and strategies for overcoming challenges.

Response: Mr. Hartanto underscored MSMEs' pivotal role in sustainability, despite their limited direct emissions. He noted that the adoption of eco-friendly practices by MSMEs can drive significant positive change due to their scale and reach. Strategies to overcome barriers include accessing financial support, leveraging government incentives, and responding to growing consumer demand for environmentally conscious products. Additionally, innovations such as recycling and waste-to-product solutions were proposed as practical methods for enhancing sustainability and competitiveness among MSMEs.

Question 5: How will the growing focus on sustainability impact future investment trends in Indonesia? This question explores the implications of sustainability for Indonesia's investment landscape.

Response: Mr. Hartanto highlighted that global and regional pressures, particularly from European markets, are driving the adoption of sustainable investment practices in Indonesia. He pointed to the increasing prevalence of **Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI)**, where institutional investors commit to allocating resources to sustainable assets. He projected that regulations will soon mandate institutions like pension funds, insurance companies, and mutual funds to integrate sustainability into their portfolios, reshaping investment priorities in alignment with global standards.

Question 6: What is the future of ESG investments in Indonesia? This question considers the growth trajectory of ESG investments in Indonesia.

Response: Mr. Hartanto forecasted significant expansion in ESG investments, supported by regulatory reforms and increasing demand from international investors. He emphasized the role of the **IDX Carbon Exchange** in positioning Indonesia as a key player in Southeast Asia's sustainable finance sector. As companies increasingly adopt ESG principles, these initiatives are expected to accelerate Indonesia's transition towards achieving its long-term sustainability objectives, reinforcing the country's commitment to global climate goals.

Conclusion

The webinar highlighted Indonesia's shift toward integrating ESG principles into its financial landscape, emphasizing the interconnectedness of financial stability and sustainable practices. Key developments, including mandatory sustainability reporting, ESG-focused indexes, and the IDX Carbon Exchange, position Indonesia as a key player in global sustainable investment. For investors, ESG-focused products like green bonds present opportunities to achieve financial returns while driving environmental and social impact. Meanwhile, businesses, especially MSMEs, can innovate and reduce carbon footprints to meet growing demand for sustainable products.

Globally, Indonesia is poised to attract foreign capital by demonstrating environmental commitment through robust carbon trading and sustainability measures. Policymakers must further strengthen regulations, incentivize ESG adoption, and align with global climate goals like the Paris Agreement. The convergence of regulatory support, global investment trends, and innovative financial mechanisms signals a promising future for sustainable finance in Indonesia. By embracing ESG principles, the nation can mitigate climate risks, foster economic innovation, and lead in Southeast Asia's sustainable finance sector.

The webinar reaffirmed that sustainable investing is now central to economic growth, blending financial success with social and environmental resilience.

Speaker's Profile

Edwin Hartanto is a finance and economics expert with a passion for the capital and carbon markets. With over 10 years of experience in the financial sector, he currently leads the Carbon Trading Development Unit at the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), focusing on building and managing Indonesia's Carbon Exchange (IDX Carbon). Edwin holds a Master's degree in Economics of Development from Erasmus University Rotterdam's International Institute of Social Studies and a Bachelor's degree in Finance from the University of Indonesia. His expertise spans capital markets, asset valuation, macroeconomics, and ESG.

Appendix 1. Presentation Deck from Webinar Session

This appendix provides access to the presentation deck used in the webinar session titled Promoting Sustainable Investment in Indonesia Capital Market. The deck outlines key insights shared during the session, including the latest trends in sustainable finance, the role of ESG in fostering responsible investment, and Indonesia's strategies for achieving sustainable economic growth.

For complete access to the presentation deck, please refer to the DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14249986](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14249986).

1st Talk Show

Navigating Uncertainty: How Global Shifts and Domestic Changes are Redefining the Future of Investment

Overview

Panelists The talk show addressed key issues such as geopolitical tensions, changes in monetary policies, and Indonesia's ambitious economic reforms. The panelists, who are professionals in the investment field, emphasized the importance of applying both long-term and short-term investment strategies, as well as the market's ability to adapt to uncertainty. This discussion also explored opportunities arising in emerging sectors. Geopolitical aspects can influence Indonesia's capital market, particularly through the country's dependence on certain countries for the supply of essential commodities. Participants gained insights on adjusting investment strategies to navigate uncertainty, manage risks, and adapt to external factors impacting Indonesia's capital market for future investment planning.

Deden Wahyudiyanto
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Introduction

The impact of Federal Reserve policies on the rupiah, the trade war between China and the US, and escalating tensions between Iran and Israel have significantly heightened global market uncertainties. These challenges, compounded by geopolitical tensions, shifting monetary policies, and international conflicts, pose substantial difficulties for investors in formulating effective strategies. On the domestic front, Indonesia's ambitious economic growth targets under the Merah Putih cabinet present great opportunities but also introduce new risks that require careful consideration.

Therefore, the theme "*The Future of Investing: Strategies for Sustainable Growth*" chosen to provide comprehensive insights and adaptive strategies for investors to navigate these evolving global and domestic dynamics.

This talk show aims to empower participants with insights into global influences, an in-depth analysis of domestic developments, and strategies to enhance market adaptability. By fostering a better understanding of these issues, the session equips investors to navigate uncertainty, leverage emerging opportunities, and adopt sustainable investment practices.

Format & Methodology

The talk show took place on Friday, November 15, 2024, from 2:00 PM to 4:00 PM (GMT+7), conducted virtually via Zoom Meeting with a total duration of 120 minutes. The event is designed to feature an engaging and interactive format that encourages active participation from both speakers and the audience. The talk show will include a 90-minute discussion session, followed by a 20-minute Q&A segment, and will conclude with a 10-minute closing statement and summary. The primary audience for this event includes students interested in sustainable investing, as well as practitioners and academics eager to deepen their knowledge. Participants are expected to gain insights into long-term growth strategies, sustainable practices, future trends, and actionable approaches to creating a positive impact on society and the environment through investment choices.

Discussions

Ambitious Economic Growth Under The New Cabinet (Merah Putih)

As we consider the ambitious economic goals set by the new Merah Putih cabinet, it's crucial to recognize the potential challenges and uncertainties that may arise. Alongside the opportunities, times of political change can introduce various risks to investors, requiring thoughtful strategies and adaptability.

In light of these considerations, the 1st talk show began by discussing Indonesia's economic growth targets under the new "Merah Putih" cabinet. Mr. Firman highlighted that while the cabinet presents significant opportunities in sectors such as infrastructure, construction, technology, and digital industries, it also comes with its own set of challenges. According to data from the University of Indonesia's Economic Study, the government aims to achieve key milestones, including an 18% growth in banking credit, a 3% decrease in unemployment, and a 7.8% increase in both investments and government spending. However, these ambitious goals are accompanied by potential challenges, such as inflation, reliance on debt financing, and global uncertainties. To navigate these dynamic market conditions, investors are advised to diversify their portfolios effectively.

Mr. Firman discussed the projected growth in the primary consumption, property, mining, and infrastructure sectors, supported by government initiatives such as the free nutritious meal program and property sector stimulus. Despite commodity price volatility, the mining sector remains attractive, while the banking sector continues to be a key economic driver, with promising opportunities in undervalued bank stocks. He emphasized the importance of investors monitoring macroeconomic conditions and carefully timing their investments in these promising sectors.

In response, Mr. Deden provided further insights on the risks associated with investing, building on analysis by identifying six key risk areas that investors should be mindful of when making decisions in the current market environment.

1. Geopolitical factors can present sudden challenges that affect the national economy, with shifts in global dynamics potentially disrupting economic stability.

2. Economic crises remain a concern, as evidenced by Indonesia's deflation over the past five months. While the government has implemented policies to address this issue, individuals, especially those aged 20-25, need to be more proactive in preparing their personal finances.
3. The inconsistency of policies in Indonesia, marked by frequent regulatory changes, adds uncertainty to both the market and investors.
4. The current market conditions are in a "discount everything" phase, with adjustments tied to the aftermath of the presidential election.
5. Currency fluctuations continue to influence interest rates and the real sector, potentially disrupting broader economic stability.
6. The increasing influence of BRICS policies is starting to challenge Indonesia's economic resilience. Overall, these risks emphasize the importance of adaptive strategies to navigate the evolving economic landscape.

Furthermore, risks often stem from the investors' own behavior. Even professionals with solid financial literacy, such as holders of the WPPE license, still make cognitive errors when predicting the market. These mistakes are often caused by a lack of understanding of long-term perspectives or limited knowledge of certain sectors. To mitigate these risks, investors should choose quality investments and diversify their portfolios into short-term, medium-term, and long-term categories. Some funds should be kept in cash for flexibility, while long-term investments are crucial for achieving future goals, such as buying a house.

Additionally, investors should avoid greed and FOMO, focusing on rational decision-making. Controlling emotions and choosing the right investment instruments are essential to minimize risks.

In line with this approach Mr. Dody, the focus should be on creating a balanced and adaptive investment plan, rather than entirely shifting towards alternative investment instruments, as Indonesia's alternative market is still in its developmental stages. He emphasized that young investors, in particular, need to pay close attention to their investment horizon and risk tolerance. Beyond fintech and peer-to-peer (P2P) lending, Mr. Dody suggested exploring opportunities to start a business, either through partnerships with peers to launch new ventures or by investing in franchises. This

approach not only diversifies investment portfolios but also encourages entrepreneurial growth.

Before making investments, particularly in alternative companies or joint ventures with friends, it is crucial to ensure several key factors. First, investors must have a clear understanding of how the business generates revenue and profits, as well as ensure that business partners or friends can be trusted. Following this, the growth potential of the company should be analyzed, including the efficiency of business operations, such as relationships with suppliers and the ability to secure inventory at favorable prices. In businesses that rely on third-party financing, such as fintech or banking, it is essential to secure capital at a low cost to subsequently lend it out at more favorable rates. Furthermore, sectors in Indonesia with growth potential, as discussed by Mr. Deden and Mr. Firman, should also be considered.

Investor Concerns Regarding The Effects of Federal Reserve Policies on The Value of The Rupiah

As we delve deeper into the impact of the new cabinet's policies, it's important to consider which sectors stand to gain the most and how investors can effectively position themselves.

One such factor that could influence sector performance is the depreciation of the rupiah, a topic Mr. Deden addressed, explaining that while the depreciation may cause some goods to become more expensive, it can also make others cheaper, presenting opportunities if viewed carefully. For example, during the 1998 monetary crisis, despite the drastic decline in the rupiah's value, the export sector, such as commodities in Sulawesi, thrived. While risks in investment are often perceived as daunting, they should not be avoided but rather recognized and managed effectively. Investors need to understand the sectors they are investing in, such as the property or mining sectors, which may currently be in decline, and focus on emerging opportunities, such as government programs supporting certain industries.

Before investing, Mr. Deden emphasized the importance of identifying risks and selecting the right investment instruments. Investment funds should be divided into short-term, medium-term, and long-term categories to manage risks more

effectively. Additionally, it is essential to allocate funds for daily and future needs. With a proper approach, such as diversifying investment funds and identifying risks, investors can minimize potential losses and maximize available opportunities.

In this context, Mr. Firman explained that while the depreciation of the rupiah may make some goods more expensive, it also creates opportunities in sectors where prices become cheaper. He cited the example of Mr. Lo Kheng Hong, whose portfolio suffered an 85% loss during the 1998 monetary crisis but still saw opportunities in undervalued stocks, such as United Tractor, which was very cheap at the time. With experience and an understanding of market patterns, Mr. Lo Kheng Hong, one of Indonesia's value investors, was able to achieve substantial profits after four years.

Mr. Firman emphasized that in investing, especially in volatile markets, it is crucial to be well-prepared and experienced while focusing on opportunities rather than being trapped by FOMO or fear. Furthermore, Mr. Firman reminded that to succeed in investing, it is important to prepare properly, including understanding technical analysis, fundamentals, and risk management. He also advised starting to invest early, as he did during his university years. By practicing, gathering data, and following market patterns, we can manage risks and seize opportunities. For long-term investing, focusing on a company's fundamentals is key, while for short-term trading, it is essential to follow a tested system.

In addition to what Mr. Deden and Mr. Firman have already explained. Mr. Dody shared his experience at Provident Capital Partner, where one of their companies, involved in nickel mining and tower businesses, faced challenges due to the depreciation of the rupiah. To manage the risk of exchange rate fluctuations, the company's management decided to refinance their USD-denominated bonds into IDR-denominated bonds. This approach highlights the importance of having a clear strategy and game plan to address challenges such as currency depreciation and other risks, as emphasized by Mr. Firman.

The Trade War between China and US and The Tension between Iran and Israel

As escalating trade tensions between the US and China continue to impact the investment landscape in ASEAN, it raises important considerations for investors navigating this uncertain environment. Furthermore, with rising tensions between Iran

and Israel affecting global oil prices and inflation, investors must find ways to navigate challenges such as the depreciating rupiah and increasing import costs

In this context, Mr. Firman discussed how geopolitical tensions and trade wars, particularly between the US and China, affect Indonesia, given its strong trade relationships with both countries. These tensions impact factors like exports, imports, and supply chains, which in turn influence the Indonesian stock market (IHSG). In recent times, factors such as China's stimulus measures, inflation in the US, and capital outflows have contributed to a significant drop in the IHSG.

As an investor, Mr. Firman's strategy is to wait for foreign capital to return to the Indonesian market before making entry decisions. He also emphasized focusing on defensive sectors, such as consumer goods, which tend to perform better during geopolitical crises. However, he cautioned about the rising cost of raw materials, like wheat. The banking sector is also considered resilient in such conditions. Overall, Mr. Firman prefers to wait for positive sentiment and foreign inflows before making investment moves in the short term.

These economic considerations are deeply intertwined with geopolitical dynamics, as tensions in different regions add further complexity to the global landscape. Mr. Deden continued by emphasizing that although Indonesia is often caught in the midst of global geopolitical tensions, such as the trade war between China and the United States or other political conflicts, Indonesia tends to remain more stable compared to other countries. This is due to the strength of Indonesia's domestic market. For example, even though Indonesia imports essential commodities such as rice, sugar, and wheat, changes in the markets or policies of supplying countries can affect the stability of supply, but Indonesia is able to adapt quickly. Mr. Deden reminded that the dependence on certain countries for commodities, such as rice from India or wheat from the United States, should always be considered in market analysis, especially when policy changes could potentially disrupt supply chains.

Furthermore, Mr. Deden highlighted the importance of understanding international relations when selecting individual stocks. He stated that investors need to be aware of how Indonesia's relations with major countries such as China or the United States can affect the Indonesian stock market, both in terms of opportunities and risks. For

instance, in recent years, despite the trade war between China and the United States, there were Indonesian companies that took advantage of the situation by supplying products previously dominated by China. Mr. Deden gave the example of a company producing glove molds, which received high demand from the United States after the country stopped importing gloves from China. This shows that complex geopolitical conditions can present both opportunities and risks, which investors need to fully understand.

In response to this, Mr. Dody acknowledged that investing in alternative instruments is quite challenging, as the regulations in this area are still not as developed as those in traditional capital markets. On the other hand, traditional markets offer clear advantages in terms of liquidity and flexibility, allowing investors to quickly shift between stocks. However, the situation is different in alternative investments, where businesses are not publicly traded and involve a higher degree of risk.

Mr. Dody shared an experience from a recent project involving a potential American partner interested in entering the digital infrastructure business, which is controlled by his company. The main difficulty faced by the partner was navigating the regulatory environment in Indonesia. He pointed out that the ease of doing business in Indonesia is relatively low, and he fully realized this when working on the project. Despite the company's financial strength and what seemed to be a mature business, they discovered they were missing basic licenses, such as the Building Permit–*Izin Mendirikan Bangunan* (IMB), and other necessary permits, which had not been arranged. The complexity arose from the significant requirements and overlapping regulations from various government agencies, making it difficult to invest in alternative markets. Moreover, he emphasized that for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), it's especially hard to assess the business accurately, as crucial information often lies behind the financial data.

The Influence of Geopolitics and Market Instability: Long-Term vs. Short-Term Investment Strategies

Building on this perspective, Mr. Dody stated that he identifies as an investor who firmly believes that investments should be made with a long-term perspective. He shared that his investment journey began during his university years, and over time, he

explored various instruments, including futures and other options. However, he has now developed a strong conviction that investments should focus on companies with solid fundamentals and be held for the long term. As Mr. Firman explained, the performance of a company's stock is closely tied to its financial performance. To determine whether a company is financially strong, one must use financial analysis tools. While financial statements are crucial, they only provide one aspect of the analysis. Other important factors to consider include the quality of management and the current state of the industry. Evaluating a company's capital structure is also essential, as different companies operate with varying mechanisms. For instance, banks heavily rely on low-cost third-party funds, whereas other companies may have different structures. Therefore, analyzing a company's performance thoroughly requires time. Nevertheless, Mr. Dody is confident that financial performance should remain the primary criterion for long-term investment decisions.

Similarly, Mr. Deden emphasized the importance of long-term investments, especially for young people in their 20s, advising consistent investing as a key strategy. For example, if one has a monthly allowance, a portion should be allocated to buying fundamentally strong stocks regularly, regardless of price fluctuations. Over time, this approach could lead to financial freedom. Additionally, he stressed the need for diversifying investments into safer options like gold, government bonds, or savings bonds, with platforms like Pegadaian and others offering accessible ways to save in gold.

While the focus should remain on long-term investments, Mr. Deden acknowledged that short-term trading is not discouraged if done with clear goals. He added that small profits from trading, such as a 3-5% spread, could be used for daily needs or leisure, like enjoying time at a café. However, he emphasized that the primary focus should be on building a secure financial future through disciplined saving, consistent investing, and diversifying assets wisely.

According to Mr. Firman, both long-term and short-term investments present opportunities, depending on the investor's characteristics. For long-term investments, the current market conditions offer a chance to buy stocks with low valuations and

strong fundamentals. At the same time, market volatility provides opportunities for short-term trading or investment, similar to the commodity boom in 2022.

Mr. Firman emphasized the importance of caution when selecting stocks for long-term investments, particularly avoiding cyclical stocks. He also recommended using the proceeds from short-term investments to increase the capital for long-term investments, which serve as the primary goal for achieving financial freedom, such as purchasing a home or preparing for retirement. For those interested in short-term investments, learning technical analysis and taking advantage of market opportunities can help grow capital without affecting long-term savings or emergency funds.

Key Questions and Responses

1. Portfolio Strategies and Uncertainty Management

Question: *Should investors focus on alternative investments or develop adaptive portfolios to navigate uncertainties? What key factors should investors prioritize in facing political and economic uncertainty?*

Response: Mr. Doddy emphasized that while alternative investments can complement a portfolio, they should not dominate it. Traditional investments, such as stocks and bonds, should remain the foundation due to their stability and predictability. Alternative investments are suitable for further diversification but require careful allocation. Regarding key factors, Mr. Doddy highlighted the importance of understanding one's risk appetite and investment horizon. Aligning investments with short-term and long-term strategies while keeping the purpose of investment clear is critical for managing risks effectively and achieving financial goals.

2. Sustainable Investments and Economic Development

Question: *How can the future of investment be designed to support sustainable growth, and what strategies should be implemented by the government, private sector, and civil society to align investments with sustainable development goals (SDGs)?*

Response:

1. **Mr. Deden:** Sustainability reports, as mandated by POJK No. 51 of 2017, are key tools for assessing corporate commitment to sustainability. While BUMN companies tend to comply better than private companies, challenges in ensuring consistent commitment remain prevalent.
2. **Mr. Firman:** Large-scale projects, such as IKN, require robust integration of sustainability frameworks, including AMDAL, PROPER, and IDX Carbon, from conceptual to technical stages. Stronger collaboration among the government, private sector, and researchers is essential.
3. **Mr. Dody:** ESG criteria are increasingly significant for foreign investors. Companies with strong sustainability practices, such as BUMN and large private entities like BCA, are better positioned to attract international investment. Strengthening ESG practices can drive more foreign investment, despite challenges in implementation.

3. Risk Management Frameworks and Tools

Question: *What risk management frameworks or tools are effective in current market conditions? Are there specific instruments to stabilize investment portfolios?*

Response: Mr. Deden recommended the Value at Risk (VaR) framework for estimating potential maximum portfolio losses over a specific time frame. VaR is a reliable tool for understanding risk exposure and making informed investment decisions.

4. Strategies to Mitigate Rupiah Depreciation Risks

Question: *What long-term strategies can investors apply to protect assets against risks such as rupiah depreciation?*

Response:

1. **Mr. Deden:** Safe-haven investments, such as gold, provide a hedge against currency depreciation. Diversifying between riskier and safer instruments protects portfolios during volatility. He shared personal experiences of using gold as a safety net, ensuring stability during market downturns.

2. **Mr. Firman:** Diversification into low-risk assets, such as USD, deposits, or money market funds, is essential. These assets provide stability and reduce vulnerability to currency fluctuations.
3. **Mr. Dody:** While diversification is critical, investors should approach foreign markets cautiously due to high transaction costs and complexity. Domestic investments offer more accessible and varied options suited to local market dynamics.

5. Identifying and Mitigating Key Risks for Local Investors

Question: *What key risks do local investors face currently, and how can they mitigate these risks while leveraging opportunities?*

Response: Mr. Deden identified market risks, including exchange rate volatility, interest rate fluctuations, and stock price movements. He recommended:

- Diversifying portfolios to include safe-haven assets like gold or deposits.
- Monitoring macroeconomic indicators to anticipate and respond to market changes.
- Maintaining flexibility to capitalize on emerging opportunities.

Conclusion

The discussion provided comprehensive insights into the complex investment landscape facing Indonesian investors. The discussion highlighted the critical importance of adaptability, strategic thinking, and comprehensive risk management in an increasingly volatile global economic environment. Speakers unanimously emphasized the need for investors to develop robust, diversified investment strategies that can withstand geopolitical tensions, currency fluctuations, and economic uncertainties. Key recommendations included maintaining a long-term investment perspective, understanding fundamental market dynamics, and carefully analyzing both domestic and international economic factors before making investment decisions.

The discussion underscored the significance of sustainable investing and the growing importance of ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) criteria. Investors were advised to not only focus on financial returns but also consider the broader impact of

their investments, particularly in alignment with Indonesia's economic development goals and global sustainable development objectives. A crucial takeaway was the importance of continuous learning, emotional discipline, and avoiding common investment pitfalls such as FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) and impulsive decision-making. The speakers stressed that successful investing requires a combination of thorough research, risk awareness, portfolio diversification, and a clear understanding of one's personal financial goals and risk tolerance.

The webinar demonstrated that while current economic conditions present significant challenges, they also offer unique opportunities for investors who are prepared, strategic, and willing to adapt to rapidly changing market dynamics. The key to success lies in maintaining a balanced approach, staying informed, and making calculated, well-researched investment choices.

Speaker's Profile

Deden Wahyudiyanto is the President Director of PT TAP Kapital Indonesia and holds certifications as a Securities Analyst (CSA), Risk Professional (CRP), and Investment Banker (CIB). He has extensive experience in corporate governance, investor relations, financial analysis, and enterprise risk management, emphasizing sustainable growth in investing.

Doddy R. Rinaldi is an experienced investment professional who has structured and executed multi-million-dollar deals across Southeast Asia and Europe. With expertise in M&A and strategic investments, he focuses on maximizing business growth while minimizing capital costs. Currently pursuing an MBA at Imperial College London, he aims to leverage his skills to drive sustainable growth and economic impact in global markets.

Firman Siregar is the founder of Kuliah Saham and a certified professional in the financial sector, holding the Certified Securities Analyst (CSA) designation, Qualified Wealth Planner (QWP), and Registered Technical Analyst from the CSA Institute.

Appendix 1. The Impact of the New Cabinet Policy, Opportunities or Challenges

This presentation material by Mr. Firman Siregar explores the implications of the new cabinet policy in Indonesia, analyzing both opportunities and challenges arising from the policy changes.

**Dampak Kebijakan Kabinet baru,
peluang atau tantangan?**

Please note that the content is presented in Indonesian. For complete access to the presentation deck, please refer to the DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14261049](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14261049).

2nd Talk Show

Navigating Risks and Opportunities: ESG Integrity, Climate Finance, and Indonesia's Urban Future

Overview

<i>Panelists</i>	The talk show offered a comprehensive exploration of sustainability challenges, focusing on ESG integration, clean technology, and environmental resilience. Discussions emphasized the importance of combating greenwashing through standardized frameworks, third-party verification, and embedding sustainability into daily operations. The role of clean technology was highlighted as critical to reducing carbon footprints and fostering resilience, with speakers discussing innovations such as HPAL technology and hybrid power systems. On environmental resilience, the session underscored the need for disaster risk management, adaptive governance, and aligning corporate strategies with local and global sustainability goals.
Arif Rahmansyah Darana <i>Specialist in Sustainability, Climate Finance, and DDR</i>	
Akmal Abudiman Maulana <i>PT Bussan Auto Finance</i>	
Chrisma Virginia <i>PT Hengjaya Mineralindo</i>	
<i>Moderator</i>	
Muhammad Ghithrif G. Putra <i>PwC Indonesia</i>	The session concluded with a clear message: achieving sustainability requires a collaborative, multi-stakeholder approach, robust governance, and a long-term vision. By integrating ESG principles and leveraging innovative solutions, Indonesia can foster resilience, drive sustainable growth, and navigate the complexities of global environmental challenges.

Introduction

The 2nd Talk show session of The 2nd Bengkulu Financial and Capital Market Summit 2024 was centered around three key topics: ESG Integration, Clean Technology, and Environmental Resilience. These discussions aimed to provide insights into how companies and investors can align their strategies with sustainability goals, navigate the challenges of greenwashing, and promote long-term resilience in Indonesia's capital markets.

Moderated by Muhammad Ghithrif from PwC Indonesia, the panel featured three distinguished speakers: Akmal Abudiman, an expert in ESG integration and sustainable finance; Chrisma Virginia, a leader in industrial process sustainability; and Arif R. Darana, a specialist in climate finance and disaster risk management.

The session explored how ESG principles are being integrated into investment decisions, the role of clean technologies in building resilience, and the importance of developing strategies for environmental resilience in the face of growing climate risks. Notably, the event highlighted the ongoing need for robust frameworks to prevent greenwashing and to ensure the authenticity of corporate sustainability efforts.

Format & Methodology

The second talk show was held on Saturday, November 16, 2024, from 9:00 AM to 11:00 AM (GMT+7), conducted virtually via Zoom Meeting. The event spanned a total duration of 120 minutes, beginning with a 10-minute opening and introduction. This was followed by a 90-minute discussion segment, a 15-minute Q&A session, and concluded with a 5-minute closing statement and summary.

The talk show adopted an engaging and interactive format, designed to encourage active participation from both speakers and the audience. The target audience included university students specializing in finance and economics, as well as practitioners and academics with an interest in sustainable investing. Participants were provided with opportunities to explore emerging trends and gain practical strategies for navigating evolving market conditions.

Discussions

The discussion segment delved into the three key topics of the session: ESG Integration, Clean Technology, and Environmental Resilience. Each of these topics was explored in depth by the panelists, who provided valuable insights into how businesses can align their operations with sustainability goals and overcome the challenges of greenwashing, climate finance alignment, and building resilience in the face of environmental risks. The speakers shared their perspectives on how to create meaningful change through strategic implementation of ESG principles, clean technologies, and comprehensive disaster risk management. The discussion also underscored the importance of embedding sustainability principles into daily operations and policy making. This includes fostering collaboration among stakeholders, implementing policies that support sustainable practices, and ensuring that investments generate both social and environmental value.

Addressing Greenwashing in ESG Integration

The discussion on ESG integration began with a shared concern over greenwashing, a significant challenge in the sustainability sector. Mr. Akmal Abudiman opened the conversation by defining greenwashing as *“misleading the public into believing that a company is more environmentally responsible than it actually is”*. He stressed that greenwashing can be avoided through standardized ESG reporting frameworks like Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), POJK 51, and Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD), which ensure transparency. Third-party verification and robust monitoring are key to verifying ESG claims and aligning them with real sustainability efforts.

Building on Mr. Akmal's point, Ms. Chrisma Virginia emphasized the importance of integrating sustainability into daily business operations. *“Sustainability should not be treated as a standalone strategy but should be embedded in the company's governance structures and day-to-day practices”*, Ms. Chrisma explained. It's crucial that sustainability is translated into actionable strategies and measurable programs to avoid greenwashing. She further stated that clear policies and strategic goals must be in place to drive real, long-term change.

Mr. Arif R. Darana then broadened the scope by adding that ESG should not only focus on reporting and operational integration but also consider regulatory frameworks and innovations in climate finance. *“To prevent greenwashing, companies need clear regulations, such as carbon trading platforms like IDX Carbon, to hold them accountable,”* Mr. Arif stated. Ultimately, ESG is an investment, not a cost, and aligning it with long-term business objectives is critical to ensuring that claims match actions.

Together, the panelists agreed that ESG integration requires a multi-faceted approach, incorporating clear reporting standards, internal operational alignment, and supportive regulatory frameworks to combat greenwashing effectively.

Building Resilience through Clean Technology and Sustainable Finance

The conversation then shifted to the critical role of clean technologies in driving sustainability and resilience. Mr. Arif R. Darana started by highlighting the importance of clean technologies such as renewable energy systems and carbon capture solutions. *“Clean technologies are not just a necessity for reducing carbon emissions, but they also help build resilience against environmental risks,”* he explained. Mr. Arif emphasized the role of carbon trading platforms, like IDX Carbon Exchange, which incentivize businesses to invest in sustainable technologies. These platforms provide the financial backing needed for companies to adopt cleaner practices, making it easier for them to transition to more sustainable models.

Following Mr. Arif’s insights, Ms. Chrisma Virginia raised concerns about the societal readiness and affordability of implementing clean technologies. While clean technologies are essential, we must ensure that their implementation doesn’t create economic disruption, especially in societies not yet prepared for rapid technological shifts. A phased approach is necessary to allow businesses and communities to adjust to these changes, balancing environmental goals with economic stability. She also shared examples from European markets where the rapid transition to renewable energy faced backlash due to its economic implications.

Mr. Akmal Abudiman agreed, stressing that clean technology must be integrated into broader ESG strategies. Technologies like renewable energy must be aligned with governance frameworks to ensure they contribute to both environmental and

corporate governance objectives. This will maximize their impact and help create long-term value for businesses while reducing environmental risks. He noted that clean technology must also meet social, economic, and governance needs to be fully effective and sustainable.

In conclusion, the panelists highlighted the need for a balanced approach to implementing clean technology—one that combines environmental benefits with economic feasibility and regulatory alignment.

Sustainable Solutions for Indonesia

The final topic of discussion focused on strategies for enhancing environmental resilience, particularly in Indonesia's context of rising climate risks. Mr. Arif R. Darana began by emphasizing the importance of disaster risk management in building resilience. Understanding local environmental risks is critical, companies must implement business continuity plans and risk-transfer mechanisms such as insurance to ensure operational stability during climate-related disruptions. Proactively identifying risks, such as floods or earthquakes, is essential for creating effective mitigation strategies.

Ms. Chrisma Virginia supported by stressing that businesses must align their sustainability efforts with local community needs. Sustainability is not just about global environmental goals, but also addressing the immediate needs of the communities where businesses operate. By focusing on local biodiversity preservation and resource management, companies can enhance their resilience and contribute to the local development of their regions. She highlighted that this local approach can provide immediate environmental benefits while aligning with broader sustainability objectives.

Mr. Akmal Abudiman emphasized the foundational role of governance in ensuring long-term resilience. Strong governance frameworks are key to ensuring that companies not only survive climate disruptions but thrive in them. Governance must serve as the backbone for all resilience-building efforts. Only with clear leadership and governance structures can businesses align their operational goals with sustainability objectives. He also noted that frameworks like POJK 51 provide businesses with clear guidelines for aligning corporate governance with sustainability goals.

The panelists agreed that building resilience requires a comprehensive strategy that integrates disaster risk management, local community needs, and strong governance frameworks. By taking a proactive and multi-dimensional approach, companies can enhance their environmental resilience and sustainability.

Key Questions and Responses

Following the insightful panel discussion, the Q&A session provided participants with an opportunity to engage directly with the speakers. Topics such as ESG integration, climate finance, and strategies to prevent greenwashing were explored in depth, offering practical and forward-looking insights.

1. Verifying ESG Claims and Combating Greenwashing

Question: *What are the most effective steps to verify companies' ESG claims and combat greenwashing?*

Response:

- **Mr. Akmal Abudiman:** Defined greenwashing as “misleading the public into believing that a company is more environmentally responsible than it actually is”. He highlighted standardized frameworks like GRI, POJK 51, and TCFD as crucial tools for ensuring transparency and accountability in ESG disclosures. He stressed the need for third-party audits to validate ESG claims and prevent greenwashing, stating, *“These frameworks ensure that sustainability efforts are measurable, verifiable, and aligned with public expectations”*.
- **Ms. Chrisma Virginia:** Emphasized integrating sustainability into daily operations through actionable strategies and realistic goals, cautioning that unattainable targets can lead to greenwashing. She added, *“It’s crucial for companies to embed sustainability practices into operations through clear policies and measurable programs”*.
- **Mr. Arif R. Darana:** Highlighted the role of regulations and carbon trading platforms, such as the IDX Carbon Exchange, in ensuring transparency and adherence to verifiable practices. He remarked, *“ESG is not just a regulatory hurdle—it’s an opportunity for long-term value creation”*.

2. Aligning Climate Finance with Environmental Outcomes

Question: *How can climate finance ensure that funded projects deliver genuine environmental benefits?*

Response:

- **Mr. Arif R. Darana:** Emphasized that climate finance must prioritize projects addressing both mitigation and adaptation, such as renewable energy initiatives and carbon capture technologies. He stated, *“Climate finance should support projects that reduce emissions and enhance resilience to climate risks”*.
- **Mr. Akmal Abudiman:** Underscored the importance of materiality assessments to align climate finance with sector-specific environmental outcomes. He explained, *“Each sector has unique ESG priorities, requiring tailored approaches. Governance is crucial in financial services, while environmental impacts dominate industries like mining”*.
- **Ms. Chrisma Virginia:** Highlighted sector-specific strategies and standards, such as IRMA for mining, to ensure sustainability goals are met. She noted, *“Tailored financing models for hybrid power systems and low-carbon initiatives are essential for driving genuine environmental outcomes”*.

3. Strategies for Sustainable Operations and Addressing Greenwashing

Question: *What strategies can companies adopt to combat greenwashing and build sustainable operations?*

Response:

- **Mr. Akmal Abudiman:** Stated that sustainability requires a long-term commitment and must be embedded in corporate governance frameworks. He added, *“Sustainability is not a one-time initiative; it’s an ongoing process of improving ESG metrics through collaboration and capacity-building”*.
- **Ms. Chrisma Virginia:** Stressed the importance of setting realistic and measurable sustainability goals. She explained, *“Overly ambitious goals can*

lead to distrust. The key is making tangible progress and maintaining flexibility to adapt to evolving environmental regulations”.

- **Mr. Arif R. Darana:** Advocated for innovative solutions, such as circular economy models and carbon-neutral technologies, to align ESG with long-term profitability. He concluded, *“ESG is not just about managing risks—it’s an opportunity for sustainable growth through innovation”.*

Conclusion

The discussion reveals a profound truth: sustainability is not a destination, but a continuous journey of intentional transformation. True environmental stewardship requires more than superficial commitments or greenwashing tactics—it demands a fundamental reimagining of how businesses understand their role in the ecosystem. By integrating rigorous governance, technological innovation, and genuine community engagement, companies can move beyond mere risk mitigation to become active architects of environmental and social resilience.

The path forward is neither simple nor linear. It requires courage to challenge existing paradigms, flexibility to adapt to evolving environmental realities, and a commitment to transparency that goes beyond compliance. Sustainability is ultimately about recognizing that corporate success is inextricably linked to the health of our shared planetary systems. It is a delicate dance of economic pragmatism and ecological responsibility, where innovation meets integrity, and short-term profits yield to long-term regenerative potential.

As the Indonesian context demonstrates, this transformation is not a global abstraction but a local imperative. By rooting sustainability strategies in community needs, understanding regional ecological risks, and creating adaptive frameworks, businesses can become catalysts for meaningful change. The future belongs to those organizations that see sustainability not as a constraint, but as the most profound opportunity for innovation, growth, and collective well-being.

Speaker's Profile

Arif Rahmansyah Darana is a specialist in water security, sustainability, and disaster risk management, focusing on climate finance. He helps cities across Asia access climate financing opportunities and translates technical insights into effective policies. With experience collaborating with organizations like GCoM Asia, UCLG ASPAC, and the World Bank, Arif is dedicated to fostering environmental resilience and securing funding for sustainable initiatives.

Akmal Abudiman Maulana is a Corporate Secretary and Investor Relations expert with over 10 years of experience in ESG and sustainable finance. A Certified Sustainability Practitioner, he excels in connecting companies with stakeholders through impactful communication and governance. Akmal leads ESG initiatives to enhance environmental and social responsibility, driving long-term business value.

Chrisma Virginia is an experienced Industrial Process Sustainability Lead at PT Hengjaya Mineralindo with a strong background in environmental compliance and pollution control. She holds multiple certifications, including the Water Pollution Control (PPPA) and Air Pollution Control (PPU) certifications, both obtained in Kutai Barat, East Kalimantan in 2023, as well as the Hazardous Waste Monitoring and Analysis (PAPLB3) certification from 2022.

Appendix 1. Sustainable Finance Milestone Indonesia

This appendix contains Mr. Akmal Abudiman’s presentation on the key milestones in sustainable finance in Indonesia from 2015 to 2024. It covers significant policy developments, regulatory frameworks, and initiatives that have shaped Indonesia's sustainable finance landscape.

Sustainable Finance Milestone Indonesia

Appendix 2. Embedded ESG Approach for Resilient Long-Term Investing Decision

This presentation material from Ms. Chrisma Virginia outlines the key principles of integrating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors into long-term investment strategies. It emphasizes how an embedded ESG approach enhances resilience, mitigates risks, and fosters sustainable value creation in the investment decision-making process.

For complete access to the presentation deck, please refer to the DOI:

[10.5281/zenodo.1426101](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1426101).

Plenary

Black Swan Events and Market Shocks: Preparing for the Unpredictable

Overview

Speaker The plenary session provided insights into systemic financial risks, highlighting the limitations of traditional models like CAPM and the Efficient Market Hypothesis. It introduced alternative frameworks such as Chaos Theory, Power-law distributions, and Antifragility, emphasizing the need for proactive risk management to mitigate endogenous vulnerabilities like excessive leverage. Participants were encouraged to focus on building resilient investment strategies capable of withstanding extreme events (tail risks).

David Dredge
Convex Strategies

Moderator

Berto Usman, PhD.
Universitas Bengkulu

The Q&A session enriched the discussion by addressing fiscal dominance in emerging markets, applying ergodic principles to volatile economies, and learning from past Black Swan events. Ultimately, financial risks are largely endogenous, stemming from internal weaknesses. Proactive prevention and adaptive, antifragile strategies are essential to ensure resilience and growth in an uncertain world.

Introduction

In the last quarter of 2023, escalating geopolitical tensions led to a global boycott of products affiliated with specific nations, significantly impacting major international corporations. For instance, PepsiCo reported a 57.5% decline in net profits to \$1.3 billion, while The Coca-Cola Company saw a 35.6% drop to \$2 billion compared to the previous quarter (Monem, 2024). These dramatic financial losses illustrate the fragility of interconnected markets when exposed to sudden, unprecedented events.

This phenomenon aligns with the concept of a Black Swan, popularized by Nassim Nicholas Taleb. A Black Swan refers to rare, unpredictable events with a disproportionate impact on systems. Historical examples such as the 2008 Global Financial Crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic highlight how these events reveal systemic vulnerabilities and challenge traditional risk management models.

The plenary session was designed to equip participants with tools to navigate these crises effectively. By critiquing conventional financial models like the Efficient Market Hypothesis and exploring alternative frameworks such as Chaos Theory, Power-law distributions, and Antifragility, the session emphasized the importance of proactive risk management and building resilience against systemic shocks. Participants gained actionable insights into addressing endogenous risks, such as excessive leverage, and developing strategies to mitigate extreme market disruptions.

This session aimed to foster a deeper understanding of risk dynamics, encouraging participants to adopt adaptive and antifragile strategies essential for thriving in today's uncertain financial landscape.

Format & Methodology

The event was conducted online via Zoom Meeting on Saturday, November 16, 2024, from 2:00 PM to 3:00 PM (GMT+7). Spanning 70 minutes, the session followed a structured format comprising a 5-minute opening, a 45-minute presentation, a 15-minute Q&A session, and a 5-minute closing. The audience included university students specializing in finance and economics, as well as practitioners and academics with a strong interest in sustainable investing. Participants gained valuable insights into emerging investment trends and practical strategies for

navigating dynamic market conditions, enhancing their academic and professional perspectives.

Discussions

The session aims to equip participants with critical insights into risk management and market dynamics. Expected outcomes include a deeper understanding of the limitations of traditional financial models, such as the Efficient Market Hypothesis and Modern Portfolio Theory, and their divergence from real-world market behavior. Participants will explore concepts like power-law distributions, chaos theory, and the distinction between endogenous and exogenous risks, gaining a fresh perspective on systemic instability and the buildup of leverage in financial systems.

Furthermore, the session emphasizes the importance of prevention in investment strategies, likened to using effective brakes in a race to ensure stability and control. Attendees are encouraged to adopt a critical approach to widely accepted assumptions in finance, such as the prevalence of Gaussian distributions, and to focus on strategies that benefit from deviations rather than relying on averages.

Practical takeaways include applying these concepts to build resilient portfolios that protect against tail risks while remaining adaptable to market shocks. The session also inspires participants to challenge established norms within academia and industry, leveraging resources like works by Benoit Mandelbrot, Nassim Taleb, and James Gleick for further exploration. Overall, the session is designed to foster a proactive mindset in managing uncertainty and complexity in financial markets.

The Plenary Session provided a platform to reexamine the foundational principles of modern finance and risk management. Central to this dialogue was the need to critically assess established models and assumptions in light of their real-world applications and limitations. Drawing inspiration from Friedrich von Hayek's *The Pretence of Knowledge*, the speaker emphasized the dangers of overly precise yet flawed methodologies that dominate the financial industry. Hayek's insight, which underscores the value of imperfect but truthful knowledge, set the tone for a deeper exploration of alternative frameworks and theories that challenge conventional financial thinking.

This session explored the dichotomy between "Sharpe World"—a term coined to describe the idealized models underpinning global finance—and the complexities of the real world. Through critical analysis, the speaker highlighted the shortcomings of widely taught financial models, such as the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) and the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH), and juxtaposed them with real-world concepts like Power-law distributions, Chaos Theory, and Ergodicity. The discussion underscored the necessity of transitioning from traditional, assumption-based strategies to robust, adaptive approaches that align with the unpredictable nature of financial markets.

Core Themes of the Discussion

1. The Illusion of "Sharpe World"

Conventional financial models, rooted in linear assumptions, often fail to account for the inherent complexity and unpredictability of markets. The speaker critiqued these models as overly simplistic, emphasizing the need for methodologies that align with chaotic real-world dynamics. Financial education often relies on models that assume linearity, normal distributions, and consistent correlations. These simplifications create a "Fantasy Land" that fails to account for the multi-dimensional and chaotic realities of financial systems. The speaker called for greater scrutiny of these assumptions and their impact on investment decisions.

2. Real-World Paradigms

The session introduced frameworks that better reflect market realities, such as Benoit Mandelbrot's Power-law distributions, Per Bak's Self-Organized Criticality, and Nassim Taleb's Antifragility. Each concept highlights the importance of embracing volatility, understanding endogenous risks, and recognizing the disproportionate impact of extreme events on long-term outcomes.

3. The Importance of Prevention

Citing Benjamin Franklin's adage, "An ounce of prevention is worth a pound of cure", and Nassim Taleb's insights on prevention, the speaker stressed the need for proactive risk management. Analogies like Formula 1 racing illustrated the idea that robust safeguards (e.g., effective "brakes") enable resilience and sustained performance over time.

4. Key Investment Insights

Using historical data, the discussion revealed the outsized influence of the best and worst months on long-term compounded returns. The analysis highlighted the inadequacy of focusing solely on mean returns and emphasized the need to design strategies that account for the magnitude of extreme outcomes.

5. Endogenous Risk and Market Fragility

Rare events often emerge from systemic vulnerabilities, such as excessive leverage, rather than external shocks. Understanding these risks is essential for mitigating cascading failures in interconnected financial systems. The session challenged the notion that crises are caused by external shocks, arguing instead that systemic vulnerabilities, such as excessive leverage, create conditions for failure. Understanding these endogenous risks is crucial for anticipating and mitigating potential market disruptions.

Key Questions and Responses

During the session, several critical issues were raised regarding the challenges and strategies for navigating today's unpredictable financial landscape. Below is a summary of the four key questions addressed, along with their core answers, providing valuable takeaways for adapting to the complexities of modern financial markets.

The Impact of Anomalies on Investment Decisions

Anomalies in financial markets challenge traditional models like CAPM and Random Walk, particularly the outdated 60/40 portfolio strategy. These anomalies push investors to adopt more adaptable strategies that focus on resilience rather than relying on artificial correlations between assets like bonds and equities.

Fiscal Dominance and Emerging Markets

Fiscal dominance is creating challenges for emerging markets by crowding out access to funding. As central banks raise interest rates, government debt burdens increase, making traditional bonds less attractive. Investors should prioritize assets that offer protection during downturns and participate in market upswings, focusing on robust strategies that thrive in extreme market conditions.

Applying Ergodicity in Volatile Markets

In emerging markets like Indonesia, investors should adopt strategies that focus on positive convexity, balancing the potential for upside participation with downside protection. Avoiding products with negative convexity is essential to managing risk and ensuring portfolios are resilient in volatile environments.

Lessons from Black Swan Events

Policymakers should focus on mitigating catastrophic risks rather than fine-tuning economic outcomes. The priority should be reducing systemic risk, such as excessive leverage, to prevent financial crises. Embracing natural volatility and preparing for extreme outcomes rather than relying on the stability of historical models is crucial for long-term economic resilience.

Conclusion

Modern financial risk management requires a shift from traditional models like CAPM and the Efficient Market Hypothesis, which often oversimplify market dynamics. Robust alternatives such as Chaos Theory, Antifragility, and Power-law distributions provide better tools for understanding and managing systemic risks, particularly those that arise endogenously, like excessive leverage and market fragility.

Key insights emphasize the importance of proactive strategies that prioritize resilience against extreme events while capturing growth opportunities. By addressing endogenous vulnerabilities and fostering adaptive approaches, stakeholders can navigate volatile financial environments with greater confidence and preparedness.

Speaker's Profile

David Dredge is the Chief Investment Officer at Convex Strategies, with over 30 years of experience in risk management across global markets. Prior to founding Convex Strategies, he served as Managing Director at Artradis Fund Management and led the EM Asia and Global trading businesses at RBS, Bankers Trust, and Bank of America.

Appendix 1. Presentation Deck from Plenary Session

This presentation, part of the plenary session, explored systemic financial risks and the limitations of traditional models like CAPM and the Efficient Market Hypothesis. Mr. Dredge introduced alternative frameworks, including Chaos Theory, Power-law distributions, and Antifragility, to address the unpredictability of black swan events.

For complete access to the presentation deck, please refer to the DOI:
[10.5281/zenodo.14261141](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14261141).

Closing Speech

Muhammad Afif Ryan Pratama

Independent Commissioner of Capital Market Study Group,
Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Bengkulu

Good afternoon, distinguished guests, speakers, participants, and friends,

As we conclude the 2nd Bengkulu International Financial and Capital Market Summit 2024, let me begin by thanking all of you for your active participation and energy throughout this event. Under the theme "The Influence of Global Issues: Strategic Planning for Long-Term Investing," we've explored crucial topics that will guide us in navigating the evolving landscape of finance and investment.

This summit has been more than just a series of discussions; it has been a journey of learning, reflection, and inspiration. Each session has left us with powerful insights:

- **Session 1** reminded us of the delicate yet essential balance between profit and responsibility. Responsible investing is not only ethical but also a driver of sustainable financial performance.
- **Session 2** highlighted the future of investing, emphasizing innovation and sustainability as the cornerstones of long-term growth.
- **Session 3** brought clarity to integrating ESG principles, showing us that sustainability is no longer optional but necessary for resilience.
- **Session 4** prepared us for the unpredictable, with valuable strategies for managing black swan events and market shocks.

Beyond these discussions, we also celebrated excellence and innovation during the **KSPM Excellence Award**. This special session recognized outstanding individuals and organizations who have shown exceptional dedication to advancing the capital market ecosystem. Their achievements remind us of the potential for impact when passion and purpose are combined. Congratulations to all the award recipients—you inspire us to aim higher in our own journeys.

Key Takeaways:

From these sessions and celebrations, several key messages resonate:

1. **Sustainability is imperative.** Financial success must align with ethical and environmental priorities for long-term impact.
2. **Adaptability and resilience are essential.** Preparing for uncertainties is as important as seizing opportunities.
3. **Innovation drives progress.** Whether in technology, strategy, or investment models, staying ahead means embracing change.
4. **Excellence deserves recognition.** Through the KSPM Excellence Award, we are reminded of the importance of celebrating milestones and inspiring future achievements.

Closing Speech (contd.)

Gratitude and Acknowledgment:

I want to express my deepest gratitude to our organizing committee, the Kelompok Studi Pasar Modal FEB Universitas Bengkulu, our speakers, sponsors, and everyone working tirelessly behind the scenes. Your efforts have been instrumental in the success of this event.

To our participants: your engagement, ideas, and enthusiasm have brought this summit to life. The discussions and connections formed here are the building blocks for future collaborations.

Looking Ahead:

As we move forward, let us carry the insights, inspiration, and momentum from this summit into our work. The global challenges we face are complex, but together, with sustainability, innovation, and strategic thinking, we can shape a resilient financial future.

Thank you all for your contributions to this meaningful event. We look forward to seeing you at future summits. With that, I officially close the 2nd Bengkulu International Financial and Capital Market Summit 2024.

Congratulations to all, and have a wonderful evening!

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